

ROLE AND PLACE OF INDUSTRIAL SECTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

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ABSTRACT

the role of the network in the economy is evaluated according to the level of production and realization of its products. In industry, products are produced that are used in all sectors of the economy - in the sectors of national economy, construction, transport, intangible production.

As you know, industry is the leading sector of the economy. Industry is considered a leading field in solving the problems of industrialization of entire social production. Therefore, during the years of independence, the work of rebuilding the material and technical basis of society, structural changes in the economy began precisely with the development of industry, in particular, its most important, leading spheres. These areas of Industry play an important role in raising the economic power of the Republic of Uzbekistan, ensuring sustainable economic growth, further improving the living well-being and quality of the population. Industry as a type of activity involves the production of material goods in the form of products and energy, that is, the extraction of Natural Resources, the processing of these resources and, as well as the processing of folk and forestry products.

Based on the generalization of opinions and opinions presented in the literature, A.In the textbook "industrial economy" by ertov, industry is defined as follows: "industry is the largest branch of material production, in which most of the labor weapons (tools), labor items and folk consumer goods are created; all types of machines and mechanisms, structural elements of buildings and structures are produced, underground resources are mined, mineral, plant and animal raw materials are processed, extensive consumer goods are prepared.[3]

A.In the opinion of platyov, the industry provides all branches of the national economy with means of production, weapons of Labor. The development of the National Economy, Science, Education, Culture, Health, Sports, Tourism and other industries depends on the level of development of the industry. The historical role of industry in the development of production forces and relations is incomparable. Therefore, the higher its development and efficiency, the higher the status of the state, and the better the standard of living of the population. Due to the development of the industry, the number of employees employed in it increases, their knowledge, professional skills increase, the personnel potential rises to a high level.

Industry produces a large part of machinery and equipment, raw materials, materials, fuel necessary for all sectors of the economy, the bulk of consumer goods. Plays a leading role in the provision of equipment to the branches of the national economy and in ensuring an increase in the economic efficiency of the entire production complex. The industrial product and the raw materials and materials used for its preparation account for 90% of the transported cargo. This, in turn, leads to the development and improvement of vehicles.

The development of industries in the national economy is mainly served by a large machine industry. The development of the machine industry can bring production productivity to a high level by embodying science and technology and other industries and arming labor with machinery. Industry, especially heavy industry, which is its most important sector, is the basis of expanded reproduction in the country. He goes on to refine socio-productive relations between members of society while reproducing material and technical means for himself and other networks.

Industry is the basis of the reconstruction of the production of the national economy. That is, material benefits in the national economy are created mainly in the manashu area. In the table below, we can understand the importance of this industry by studying its share of GDP. Competition - a force that ensures the acceleration of economic development - also arises, first of all, in industry and begins to develop. In the Republican industry, too, competition rises from its ordinary stage to its highest, becoming a truly common handle. By providing it with new techniques, it helps to raise farmers, peasant farms and subjects operating in other forms to a higher level economically and culturally, to lose serious differences between the city and the people, to transform peasant Labor into industrial labor. The following table can be traced back to the fact that the industry has constantly become a locomotive of the economy in which the share of the sectors of our national economy in GDP is reflected.

From the above figures, it can be concluded that over the past 3 years, it is possible to see that about 45% of the total created material and intangible goods were created in industry (in the case of the addition of construction). These figures mean that the industry is the leading locomotive network of our economy. It is also second in the gross value added of networks, behind the services sector, with 34%. These figures also prove that the industry is from important sectors.

Table 1.

GDP structure by types of economic activity in the industry of Uzbekistan
(in % of total)

Specification	2019	2020	2021
I. GDP, totalling, including:	100,0	100,0	100,0
gross value added of networks	88,9	90,6	90,8
net taxes on products	11,1	9,4	9,2
II. Gross value added of networks	100,0	100,0	100,0
Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries	14,3	14,4	15,0
industry (including construction	41,1	40,8	40,5
Industry	33,8	33,5	33,3
Construction	7,3	7,3	7,2
Services	44,6	44,8	44,5
trade, living and catering services	8,6	8,6	8,8
transportation and storage, information and communication	10,0	9,1	8,7
other service networks	26,0	27,1	27,0

Source: <https://stat.uz/>

Industry is the material basis for strengthening the country's defense capabilities, an important area that ensures the independence of countries. The political, economic and organizational aspirations of all countries, cooperation in economic terms, are also expressed in the industrial sphere. The importance of the industry is also considered significant in the expansion of opportunities for the use of natural, labor resources, achievements in science and technology. For the industry, the continuous progress of Science and technology and the increase in the level of armament with the achievements of production are characteristic. It makes extensive use of advanced advances in electrification, production automation, computerization and chemicalization. Uses them for peaceful purposes. Industry, especially its priority areas, is the key to solving the problems of globalization of entire production.

Only a large machine - made industry, which is dared to rebuild all sectors of the national economy, can be the one-to-one material basis of independence. The role of industry in increasing the employment of the population of the country is incomparable. The share of the general working population in the industry of the Republic is considered significant. More than 60% of the available labor resources are occupied in the industry. The rapid development of the industry of the Republic is the basis for the rise in the level of employment of labor resources. The rapid development of the network leads to an increase in the number of qualified personnel and a further increase in their position in society. The laws of development ensure the growth of the cultural and technical level of employees, the inexhaustible increase in production skills and experience.

The extraction and preparation of the existing natural resources in the country the processing of products grown in the field of national economy is carried out precisely in industrial sectors. In industry, weapons of Labor and production are created for all sectors of the economy. As you know, the weapons of Labor and production determine the development of technology, allow you to increase the productivity of human labor. The development of industry and its industries will give rise to the unilateral development of production forces. In the country and its constituent territories, it creates the opportunity to comprehensively and

efficiently use natural resources, raw materials and labor resources. The emergence and development of industry is closely related to the growth of the division of Labor, the intensification of production. Modern large industries are formed from multiple branches of industries and manufacturing that are closely related to each other.

Today, Uzbekistan is a rapidly developing country with a socially oriented market economy. The development strategy selected by the leadership of our state is aimed at the production of competitive, exportable and import substitutes, high value-added products, which provides for stable and balanced growth of the industry and the development of its leading sectors on the basis of modernization of production capacities, technical and technological renewal.

The experience gained during the thirty years of independent development of our country is confirmed by the fact that the industry, which is the basis of the economy of any state, is able to prosper on the basis of integration and at the level of demands of the world community. It is a difficult task for us to improve our economy now, having foreseen the complex tasks facing the weakly developed and deformed economy of Uzbekistan during the former regime. About this, our President Sh.Mirziyoyev said: "We pay special attention to the formation of an innovative economy, the creation of a modern industry, a favorable investment climate, the expansion of cooperation with foreign countries and leading companies. The launch of the Tashkent metallurgical plant, which is unique in all respects today, is another practical manifestation of our efforts in this regard." [26]

In other words, it is to build a powerful processing industry in the Republic, equipped with modern technology and technology, and thus provide employment for continuously growing labor resources, achieve a high increase in the national income of the Republic and reach the level of harmoniously developed republics in every way in our country."

Thus, the head of our state, who set the goal of raising the economy of Uzbekistan to the level of the economy of rapidly developing countries of the world, developed a specific model of the transition to a socially oriented free market economy, based on five principles of gradual reforms. It is known that this model, selected for the economic development of the young independent republic, today received high recognition from the world community and received the title "Uzbek model".

As a result of the consistent implementation of the proposed reforms, stability and proportionality of economic growth were ensured. For the next 5 years, the annual growth rate of the gross domestic product of the Republic of Uzbekistan is on average around 5-7 percent. In general, during the years of independence, the economy of Uzbekistan grew almost 6 times, and the real income of the population almost 9 times.

The gross domestic product per capita, on the other hand, increased to US \$ 1,750 and allowed Uzbekistan to be among the countries with average income. In the complex conditions of the transition period, special attention was paid to the development of the base sectors of the economy - oil and gas, gold production, non-ferrous metallurgy, chemical and petrochemical industries. This served to further strengthen the macroeconomic stability of our state.

President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev said in a speech at his meeting devoted to the analysis of work on industrial development, production of oil and gas products and regular supply to consumers: "Industrial Development ensured an increase in export

volume by 24 percent. In particular, exports of light cars increased by 3.3 times, buses by 2 times, trucks by 1.5 times, transformers and batteries by 2.7 times, cable-stayed products by 2.2 times, shoes by 2.1 times. Finished knitwear and tailoring products increased by 25%, knitted fabrics by 31%, finished textiles by 38%, food products by 14%, non-ferrous metals and products from them by 45%, and black metal products by 54%.[27]

Due to the positive changes made in the economy of Uzbekistan during the independence period, a significant diversification of its structure was achieved. The establishment of a number of completely new industries in the automotive industry, including the production of engines and spare parts, oil and gas chemistry, oil and gas machinery, modern national economy machinery, construction materials industry, railway machinery, production of consumer electronics tools, pharmaceutical and microbiology, food, textile, leather and footwear industry, as well as a number of other completely new industries set the stage for this. In Samarkand, bus-producing Isuzu (Japan) and truck-producing man (Germany) plants, Bukhara oil refinery, Shurtan gas-chemical complex and recently Ustyurt gas-chemical complex were put into operation, Fergana oil refinery was completely reconstructed. As a result, significant qualitative changes took place in the network structure of the industry of Uzbekistan. This is also confirmed by the following figures: the share of the industry considered a locomotive of economic growth is about 35%, at the same time the share of the national economy has gradually decreased to 18%, while the share of services has increased from 33% to 47%. Such changes are characteristic of rapidly developing economies.

In the Industrial Complex, 40% of the main funds in the national economy are embodied, which make up a significant part of the national wealth of the country. The main funds of industrial production grew by 50 times during the period 1991-2020. The role of the fuel and energy complex in industrial development is special, and its structure includes energy, oil and oil processing, gas and gas condensate, coal mining and a number of other small industries. The contribution of this complex is almost 30 percent in industrial production. The Republic of Uzbekistan is one of 10 gas producing countries in the world.

The fuel industry of the Republic is formed and developing on the basis of coal, oil, gas fields found and mined underground. About 160 oil and gas fields have been opened in the Republic, 115 of which are located in the geological province of Bukhara and Khiva, 27 in the Fergana Valley, 10 in Surkhandarya, 7 in Ustyurt. The gas industry is the youngest, highly developed sector of the fuel and energy complex. At present, natural gas production is 68 billion m³. The contribution of gas in the balance of fuel mined in the Republic is equal to 90.1 percent.

The Republic has a well-developed coal industry, and Uzbekistan has 2 billion tons of coal reserves sought after. The Angren mine is mined for brown coal, while the Sharghun and Boysun mines are mined for Stone. A special place in the economy of Uzbekistan is occupied by the metallurgical sphere of industry. Non - ferrous metallurgy is one of the most important, leading branches of Republican metallurgy. The Joint-Stock Production Association "Uzbekistan Metallurgical Combine" in Bekabad operates in the field of ferrous metallurgy.

The Republic ranks 7th in the world for gold mining and second among CIS countries after Russia. And in terms of gold mining per capita, it ranks first in the world. Forbes also mentioned the world's largest open — pit gold mine in Uzbekistan, the Muruntov mine. The publication also noted that this mine may be the largest gold reserve in the world. Recall that

earlier it was reported that the Muruntov mine, located in the Navoi region, took the first place in the list of the largest mines in the world for gold mining in 2020, which Kitco [2] announced.

The Muruntov mine, which is considered the largest on the Eurasian continent, with a high content of gold in its ore content, is among the world's giant deposits. The discovery of this deposit was hailed by the geology community of halcaro as the greatest discovery of the second half of the 20th century in gold mining. In addition to these, such industries as mechanical engineering, chemical and petrochemical, light industry occupy an important place in the industrial complex of Uzbekistan.

This network mainly includes the release of natural gas, oil, coal. Uzbekistan has large reserves of natural gas. Gas production in the Republic is increasing from year to year. For example, in the structure of the mining industry and open-pit processing, the share of the oil and natural gas production industry in January-March 2020 was 76.4%, while its physical volume index was 84.4%, according to the results of January-March 2021, the share of the oil and natural gas production industry was 69.6%, while the physical volume index compared to the corresponding period last year decreased som. The volume of products produced by electric, gas, steam supply and air conditioning Enterprises is 7.9 trillion. the sum was (8.7% of the total industrial output).

If in the early years of independence the main goals in our Republic were aimed at short-term prospects, at the same time due to high rates of economic growth, macroeconomic stability and active structural updates, the possibility of setting and implementing priority tasks for medium and long periods arose.

Today, the main goal of long-term economic policy is to develop industries that have advantages in forming a sustainable chain of processing available raw materials reserves, to create a competitive, stable, structurally proportional economy due to the rapid development of high-tech processing industries that serve to increase the value-added product. In this direction, in the following years, the industry of our country has mastered the preparation of electrical equipment, polyethylene, polypropylene, parts and components for machinery and other industries, household electrical equipment - washing machines, gas plates, air conditioners, vacuum cleaners, a number of other types of high-tech products. As a result, to date, more than 60 percent of the industrial output produced in our country has fallen on the contribution of completely newly established industries in the years of independence. In addition to the above points, the role of the industry in ensuring employment is considered significant. To date, only a large part of the employed population operates in the industry.

Table 2

Employment in various sectors of the industry of our country (in%, 2021)

Network name	The share of slaves with total work is in %
Industry	18,8%
including:	
agriculture and forestry	27,7%
construction	9,6%
transport and communication	5,4%
trade and catering	4,3%
Social sphere	10,9%
Remaining areas	23,3%

Source: <https://mineconomy.uz/uz/info/1242>

According to the balance of labor resources, in 2021, the total labor resources of the Republic are 18.3 million people, of which 99.4 percent constitute the working population and the rest are working adolescents and pensioners. In addition, it is worth noting that 75.3% of labor resources or 13.8 million belong to the category of economically active population, of which 13.1 million belong to the category of working population.

From the table above, we can conclude that industry is considered the second largest industry that employs the population. Bolsak, which says By Numbers, 18.8% of the population of 13.1 million people, i.e. about 2.5 million people, operate in industry. It can be seen from this that the evolutionism of the industrial sector and the establishment of more productive entities contribute to the reduction of the unemployed in their own right.

In the period after our independence, as a result of the above, the volume of production of industrial products increased by 4.6 times, in the next 10 years, the average annual growth rates of the industrial sector exceeded the growth rates of GDP. While high, it was 8.9 percent. Reference point: in the 90s, about 33% of the country's gross domestic product fell on the share of Agriculture, and in turn, industrial products did not exceed 14%. Also, the basis of industrial products was the production of cotton ginning and agricultural machinery products.[25]

It should be noted that the development of industries, the increase in the volume of deeply processed products, the effective organization of the import of industry into the village is expanding the possibilities of proportionally placing production forces in the regions. As a result of the work carried out on employment in 2021, the following landscape was formed in the structure of the networks:

At the same time, Uzbekistan has adopted a comprehensive strategic program aimed at further reforming the economy, deepening structural changes and diversifying until 2020. It combined eight complex programs that are inextricably linked: reliable protection of private property, increasing its share and importance in the economy, introducing modern corporate management methods, modernization and diversification of production, localization of

finished products, development of engineering and communication and road transport infrastructure, reducing the volume of energy consumption in the economic sectors and social sphere, and ensuring the introduction of energy-saving technologies.

As a conclusion, it should be noted that the industrial complex is the leading branch of the economy of the Republic, and its progress serves to increase the economic potential of the country, to make its economy a solid place in the world economic system.

President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev's address to the parliament dedicated to the results of the socio-economic development of our country on December 29, 2020 and the most important priorities of the economic program for 2021, 161 large industrial facilities were launched in the short term, despite the 8.5 percent increase in the volume of industrial production and a pandemic in our country. It was mentioned that this will allow us to produce an additional 1.5 trillion soums in the coming year. [24] at the same time, it was also noted that it is necessary to ensure the rapid development and support of industries and enterprises, which, first of all, can compete equally in the world market and at the next stage become a locomotive of economic growth, further modernization and diversification of the economy, as well as precisely oriented support.

Therefore, it will be necessary to consistently reform the economy of our country, deepen the structural transformation and diversification, ensure the rapid development of new enterprises and production networks based on high technologies, and further accelerate the processes of modernization and technical updating of operating capacities. This is an important factor in achieving competitiveness and reaching world markets.

The reforms carried out in our country in recent years, strengthening the material technical base of the industry and opening a wide path to production from the legal side are paying off. In this regard, our President Sh.M.According to the decree of Mirziyoyev "on additional measures to increase the industrial potential of the regions", the rapid development of domestic industry was made the top priority.[1] at the time of this decision, we can see that the importance of the industrial sector today is higher than ever.

In raising the economy of our country, it is of paramount importance to increase the economic potential of industrial enterprises. Because, through the development of the industrial sector, the opportunity arises to make the most of all the natural, labor and financial resources of the country, as well as all the achievements of Science and technology. And the effective and rational use of these opportunities plays an important role in raising the economic potential of our country and bringing the industry to a new level. To date, the conduct of economic development, tied to industry, plays an important role in a diversifying approach to production systematically.

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